

THE ROLE OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL, AND SPIRITUAL CAPITAL IN IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE (CASE STUDY IN BANDA ACEH CITY TOURISM INSTITUTION)

AGUS ARIYANTO¹, MUHAMMAD ADAM*², SAID MUSNADI³ and MUSLIM⁴

¹Ph.D. Student, Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia.

*^{2,3,4}Lecturer, Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia.

* Corresponding Author: Email: muhammadadam@unsyiah.ac.id

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to analyze the role of intellectual capital and spiritual capital to improve organizational performance the tourist government in Banda Aceh City, mediated by the Organization Citizenship Behavior variable. The subjects of this study were the employees of the Banda Aceh City Tourism Office with a sample of 75 people using convenience sampling technique, while the data were analyzed using Pearson correlation. Data analysis method in this study uses multiple regression and Bootstrapping (PROCESS) used to test and explain causal relationships between variables shown in a series of path analysis models. Results analysis obtained: (1) the influence of intellectual capital on organizational performance proved to have a positive and significant relationship, namely a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ (H1 is accepted), (2) the direct influence of spiritual capital on organizational performance is -0.070 , (3) the effect of mediation proved significant with an indirect effect coefficient of 0.273 , and (4) the effect of mediation proved significant with an indirect effect coefficient of 0.458 , with a confidence interval (CI) of 95% at Boot LLCI (lower level for CI) is 0.227 and Boot ULCI (upper level for CI) is 0.676 .

Keywords: Halal Tourism, Intellectual Capital, Spiritual Capital, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and Organizational Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rate of growth Islamic economy that is currently growing rapidly, one of which is the syariah tourism sector. Syariah tourism has a difference compared to religious tourism, namely that the Indonesian people know that they are limited to visit of the graves scholars, mosques, and other Islamic heritage sites.. Now, The Islamic economic sector is a potential dimension to be developed in the midst of the global economy. The Islamic Economy consists of at least 7 dominant sectors whose development is increasing, namely the culinary field, Islamic banking, pharmacy, entertainment, insurance, fashionable, types of cosmetics, and tour, all of which adhere to the halal concept in each of their products. Currently the halal industry has undergone changes/evolution to financial products (such as insurance, banking, etc.), as well as various other living cultural needs products (such as hospitals, treatment, tour, and recreation).

The growing world community is the reason that the growing trend of sharia tourism in many countries in the world. Projection of world population growth based on religion from 2010 to 2050 as published by the Pew Research Center research institute (2015), In 2010 the Muslim population was 1.599 billion or 23.2% the country's total population and in 2050 it is estimated

that the Muslim population in the world will reach 2.761 billion or about 29.7% population total of the world. In 2010 to 2050, the population will grow to reach 1.161 billion people. It is estimated that the increase in the number of Christians until 2050 is only 749 million. The second largest population is Muslims after Christians, which amounted in 2.168 billion to 2010 or 31.4% total population of the whole country. Table 1 below presents data on the growth rate of the world's Muslim population compared to the population of other religions.

Table 1: Total World Population Growth by Religion Forecast in 2010 – 2050

	World Population 2010	% World Population 2010	Population Projection 2050	% World Population 2050	World Population Growth 2010– 2050
Christians	2.168.330.000	31,4	2.918.070.000	31,4	749.740.000
Muslims	1.599.700.000	23,2	2.761.480.000	29,7	1.161.780.000
Unaffiliated	1.131.150.000	16,4	1.230.340.000	13,2	99.190.000
Hindus	1.032.210.000	15,0	1.384.360.000	14,9	352.140.000
Buddists	487.760.000	7,1	486.270.000	5,2	-1.490.000
Folk religions	404.690.000	5,9	449.140.000	4,8	44.450.000
Other religions	58.150.000	0,8	61.450.000	0,7	3.300.000
Jaws	13.860.000	0,2	16.090.000	0,2	2.230.000
World total	6.895.850.000	100,0	9.307.190.000	100,0	2.411.340.000

Source: the future of world religions: population growth projections 2010-2050 (PEW research center, 2015)

This is similar to the data published by the Standard Dinar (2016) in the State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2020/2021, where the growth of the world's halal sector is experiencing advanced development. For example, in the halal food and beverage industry, it increased by 3.1% in 2019 by \$1.13 trillion, increasing to \$1.17 trillion, and is predicted to decrease slightly in 2020 due to the covid-19 pandemic, but will continue to grow to reach \$1.38 trillion in 2024. Travel and tourism also experienced an increase, namely in 2019 Muslim spending on travel was recorded at \$194 billion and decreased due to the Covid-19 pandemic to \$58 billion in 2020, but the trend of increasing travel will occur after the pandemic begins in 2023. Optimistic that the tourism industry will recover, one of which is marked by tourism service provider sites such as Traveloka Indonesia, which generated revenue of \$250 million in July 2020. While expenditure on clothing (Muslim fashion industry) in the world earned revenue of \$277 billion in 2019, and experienced a slight decline of 2.9% to \$268 billion in 2020. Muslim spending on clothing will grow again in the next 5 years by 2.4% from 2019 to 2024 to reach \$311 billion in 2024. Referring to these data, the huge potential market Muslim of the world looks tempting for tourism entrepreneurship players, both global and domestic business players.

The tourism sector is an important factor in the development and development of an area. Some parts of Indonesia have made the tourism sector the main target in increasing regional income and a source of income for the surrounding community. Even the current tourism trend that is developing is syariah tourism. Syariah tourism activities or activities in their development have now become a very advanced tourism sector in Indonesia but also at international level. Aceh

region that applies Islamic rule in the governance system of government and social society, It can be seen that currently syariah tourism has considerable potential to be able to develop in Aceh. Of course, I really hope that syariah tourism that appears in Aceh will be able to provide great economic benefits for the entire community, thus making it one of the main syariah tourist destinations in the archipelago, via Banda Aceh City Tourism Office must be able to improve. Clean up by providing facilities through policies/regulations, the availability of tourism infrastructure and not tourism infrastructure. What is meant by not infrastructure is readiness of the Human Resources.

Developing syariah tourism in Indonesia does not escape the important role of human resources who work in tourism offices throughout Indonesia as organizational resources. If there is no strong intellectual capital support, Syariah tourism in the province will be difficult to develop. Implementation of tourism in Aceh in order to develop requires orderly regulations that are in favor of the development of the world of tourism and various strategies are formulated to promote targeted tourism areas which are the heavy responsibility of the Banda Aceh City tourism office and the surrounding community.

The intellectual aspect of employees can gain of success the an organization, Furthermore, it can influence employees in acting on their organizations, including aspects of spirituality and organizational citizenship behavior. according to Palmer and Wong (2013) intrinsic rules of spirituality can control how an employee acts under certain conditions. Even spiritual values will motivate employee behavior to be able to make a good contribution to and for community organizations (Baker & Smith, 2010). Role organizational citizenship behavior is also crucial because employees who have organizational citizenship behavior will increase organizational efficiency and effectiveness (Chelagat et al, 2015).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Intellectual Capital

The concept of intellectual capital as an intangible asset of an organization or company has a major influence on the company's resource supply process. In research Ornek and Ayas (2015) states that intellectual capital is basically a resource and synergizes with knowledge, experience, findings, updates, shopping place segments and containers that can have an effect on company performance. Intellectual capital plays an important role as a unit that includes skills, experience, inventions, innovations, market share and community that can affect company performance (Clarke et al, 2011). According to Sumedrea (2013) intellectual capital is the future center point of every organization. Intellectual Capital includes knowledge to increase company value such as; managerial, consumer, technology, suppliers, and patent processes. Intellectual Capital has 3 main resources, namely namely human capital, structural, and relational capital (Chang and Lee, 2012).

2.2. Human Capital

In the company, human capital plays an important role in ensuring that all operational and non-operational activities of the company run optimally. Human capital can create a competitive advantage if the company is able to optimize the utilization and development of the knowledge, skills and competencies possessed by its employees effectively and efficiently. Ariawan et al, (2016) states that human capital is a resource or asset of high value for the company. Khalique et al (2015) argue that human capital the most important component of intellectual capital which includes skills, organizational compliance, and employee encouragement play an important role in business organizations.

2.3. Structural Capital

Structural capital is a concept that emphasizes organizational mechanisms and structures. Hsu & Fang (2009) describe structural capital consisting of intangible assets and technological infrastructure that facilitates the flow of knowledge with the aim of increasing the company's operational efficiency. Structural capital acts as a systemic and a structure that helps achieve employee work requirements so that they reach the maximum point of intellectual performance and company performance. The core processes of the company basically depend on the performance of employees in carrying out the company's daily operations.

2.4. Relational Capital

According to Ariawan et al, (2016) relational capital as the value formed from the relationship that an organization builds on consumers and their marketing channels. Relational capital is formed maintain and build good relationships between organizations, employees and work groups because these relationships can have a strong influence on the survival of a company (Mondal & Ghosh, 2012 in Obeidat et al, 2017). Halim (2010) stated that the RC includes five indicators, namely consumer relations, supplier relations, investor relations, public relations, and relations with partners. Furthermore, the company's of there are two types of stakeholders, namely; internal stakeholders and external stakeholders. Internal stakeholders of the company are employees who work for the company, while external stakeholders consist of consumers, suppliers, government, and investors.

2.5. Spiritual Capital

The concept of spiritual capital has long been used in many fields of science, including management and leadership. Gracia (2012) argues that spiritual capital is a company asset that continues to grow in employees. It will be very useful when not engineered by the company. Some researchers define spiritual capital as the capacity of groups and Individuals are generated through the assertive process the intrinsic values of spirituality, which are able to control one's behavior under the right conditions. According to Farsani et al (2013 in Malik & Tariq 2016), spiritual capital and employee character are key factors for the success of an organization. Baker & Smith (2010) state that spiritual capital is a value and a valuable future vision to motivate individuals to contribute to society. Spiritual capital should be used as a separate resource in order to obtain increased company business results.

2.6. Organizational Citizenship Behavior

According to Kumar et al (2009) organizational citizenship behavior as a form of employee personal attitude that is voluntary, useful for the institution, does not expect recognition from the institution, and is voluntary. Organizational citizenship behavior as a person's voluntary attitude in socializing and helping each other (Sawitri et al, 2016). Podsakoff et al, (Sadeghi et al, 2016) concluded that organizational citizenship behavior can be categorized into 7 types, including: (1) sportsmanship, (2) individual growth, (3) help-oriented behaviors, (4) organizational commitment, (5) individual innovation, (6) self satisfaction, and (7) civic virtue, Furthermore, it is necessary to know that organizational citizenship behavior is an attitude that has the following characteristics: a) not as an official main duty for employees (Kaur and Kaur, 2014), b) is not mandatory, c) will not be compensated by the company's reward system, and d) is important for the success of organizational performance (Johnson et al, 2009). Based on the magnitude of the benefits that will be obtained by the company on organizational citizenship behavior, company management must be able to motivate employees to behave in a organizational citizenship behavior making a controlled and honest work environment, even special awards need to be given to employees who have organizational citizenship behavior (Jiao et al, 2011).

2.7. Organizational Performance

Many modern studies define organizational performance as the company's ability to generate corporate profits in terms of its finances (Chang and Lee, 2012), for example return on investment (ROI), return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), and others. Ling and Hong (Chang and Lee, 2012) describes the achievement of company performance as the achievement of various organizational units involved in achieving the organization's vision and mission. In the research of Maltz et al (2003) the measurement of organizational performance has 5 indicators including: financial aspects, customer/market aspects, process aspects, development aspects, and future aspects. From this explanation, organizational performance indicates the level of achievement of the institution tasks in implementing the targets, mission, vision and goals of an institution.

2.8. Intellectual Capital Relationship on Organizational Performance

In the research results of Clarke et al (2011) revealed that there is a significant influence between intellectual capital on company performance. Human capital and spiritual capital in addition to having a positive and significant relationship to company performance, also act as moderating variables. Asiaei & Jusoh (2015) explain that the determining factors in the development of 3 dimensions of intellectual capital are: (1) human capital, (2) spiritual capital, and (3) relational capital. Furthermore, Asiaei & Jusoh (2015) state that there are three dimensions of intellectual capital that can improve organizational performance in a number of companies that are the object of research. While the results of research by Abdullah and Sofian (2012) revealed that intellectual capital has a positive and significant effect on company performance, while the component of relational capital is the main predictor of performance.

Hypothesis 1: Intellectual capital has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance

2.9. Spiritual Capital Relationship on Organizational Performance

Abdullah and Sofian (2012) revealed that spiritual capital have positive and significant effect of company performance, where spiritual capital is one of the main predictors of performance. In addition, Malik & Tariq (2016) stated that spiritual capital affects organizational performance, later it was found that spiritual capital positive impact on the company's financial performance, as an indicator of performance in general. This research was supported by Gracia (2012) which emphasizes that spiritual capital has a positive effect on company performance. Spiritual capital is assumed to be a form of intelligence to provide a source of reinforcement to employees.

Hypothesis 2: Spiritual capital has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance.

2.10. The Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior As a Mediating Variable

From the many empirical evidences from previous research, it turns out that there is still an insignificant relationship between intellectual capital and organizational performance, as in the research conducted by Clarke et al. (2011) which revealed that one of the components of Intellectual Capital is structural capital which is not proven to have a significant effect on company performance. Meanwhile, Mondal and Ghosh (2012, in Obeidat, et al., 2017) prove that SC has no effect on increasing return on assets (ROA) and return on investment (ROI). Meanwhile, research by Hsu and Fang (2009) proves that there is no significant relationship between relational capital and structural capital on product development performance.

The research by Hsu and Fang (2009) proves that there is no significant relationship between relational capital and structural capital on product development performance. And there is still a relationship that is not proven to be empirically significant between spiritual capital and organizational performance, as found in the results of Minon's research (2017). Because there are still inconsistencies in the results of previous studies regarding the relationship of intellectual capital to organizational performance (research gaps), so researchers raise organizational citizenship behavior variables as mediators (intervening/mediation variables) the relationship between intellectual capital (human capital, structural capital, and relational capital). and spiritual capital on organizational performance.

So that in various previous studies it has been able to become a reference for researchers that the variable organizational citizenship behavior has proven capable of being a mediator between intellectual capital and organizational performance. For example, in the research of Andrew and Cazares (2015) organizational citizenship behavior acts as a mediator and organizational citizenship behavior can improve performance in an organization. This research is related to the relationship of organizational trust on employee productivity, with organizational citizenship behavior as a mediating variable.

Hypothesis 4: OCB mediates the relationship between spiritual capital on organizational performance.

III. METHOD

This type of research is using the survey method. Data collection uses a Likert Scale which is directed to employees who work at Tourism institution the Banda Aceh City. Sample technique using convenience sampling. The questionnaire data is said to be valid if the Pearson correlation value $> r$ table (0.227), while the reliability test uses Cronbach's Alpha ($CR > 0.70$). The data analysis method uses multiple regression.

Figure 1: Research Model

Measurement intellectual capital variables used indicators namely: skills, infrastructure and systems, knowledge and expertise, attitudes and intellect, policies, customer satisfaction and loyalty (Khalique et al, 2015); measurement of spiritual capital variables using indicators of religious knowledge, ethical values (Khalique et al, 2015). Measurement of OCB variables using indicators of sportsmanship, civic virtue, conscientiousness, and altruism (Sadeghi et al, 2016). While organizational performance variables use indicators of consumers or markets, human development processes and the future (Maltz et al, 2003).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Based on the results of the questionnaire, the demographic data of the respondents is obtained as shown in Table 1, giving an overview of male respondents totaling 41 people (55%), then female respondents amounting to 34 people (45%). The majority of employees working at the Banda Aceh City Tourism Office are 25-29 years old (20%) and 30-34 years old (20%), with the majority of them working more than 6 years (29.3%).

Table 2: Descriptive Data of Research Respondents

Demographics	Type	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Man	41	55,0
	Woman	34	45,0
Age	20-24	8	10,6
	25-29	15	20
	30-34	15	20
	35-39	25	33,3
	>40	12	16
Years of service	2 year	11	14,6
	3 year	13	17,3
	4 year	12	16,0
	5 year	17	22,6
	> 6 year	22	29,3

Source: SPSS output

Table 3: Testing Validity of Questionnaire

Construct	Pearson Correlation									df = 73
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	P= 0,05
Capital intellectual	,664	,736	,742	,792	,462	,270	,646	,532	-	r table 0,227
Spiritual Capital	,576	,443	,586	,574	,533	,552	,373	,538		
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	,392	,535	,574	,615	,524	,629	,573	,518	-	
Organizational Performance	,592	,618	,572	,574	,621	,384	,581	,522	,533	

Source: SPSS output (processed data)

Table 3 shows results the questionnaire validity test, where the questionnaire items are assumed to be valid if they have a Pearson correlation value > r table (0.227). The test results on 33 questionnaire items showed that all questionnaire items were valid. While the reliability of the questionnaire can be seen from Table 4. The research variable is said to have a level of reliability if it has a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.70. On the spiritual capital variable, cronbach's alpha value is 0.634, organizational citizenship behavior variable with cronbach's alpha value is 0.758 (<0.70) and the value is 0.6 is still accepted (Hair et al, 2006, p. 102), so all the variables studied have been obtain a fairly good reliability.

Table 4: Testing Reliability of Questionnaire

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha
Capital intellectual	0,773
Spiritual Capital	0,634
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,758
Organizational Performance	0,767

Source: outpus SPSS (data processed)

The hypothesis test in this study uses the multiple regression method, that this method is tested and provides clarity of causal relationships between research variables shown in a series of path analysis models (Cooper and Schindler, 2011, p. 530). From the multiple regression analysis carried out, the results are listed in Table 5, where it is known that all hypotheses are positively and significantly supported ($\text{sig} < 0.05$).

Table 5: Research Hypothesis Testing

Construct	Sig	Correlations	F test	R Square
Intellectual Capital	0,000	0,603	20,050	0,598
Spiritual Capital	0,824	-0,031	Sig=0,000	

Dependent Variable : Organizational Performance

Source: SPSS output (data processed)

The display in Table 5 produces a hypothesis test, the influence of intellectual capital on organizational performance is proven to have a positive and significant relationship, namely a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ (H1 is accepted). The influence of Spiritual Capital on organizational performance is proven to be insignificant, ie a significant value of $0.824 > 0.05$ (H2 is rejected). Simultaneous test The effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable is shown through the results of the F test. Where it is known simultaneously that there is an influence of intellectual capital and spiritual capital on organizational performance (Test $F = 20,050 > F \text{ table} = 2.73$). The magnitude of R square is 0.598, which means that as much as 59.8% of the variation of intellectual capital and spiritual capital affects the organizational performance variable, while as much as 40.2% is outside the model for other variables.

Testing the Mediation Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior Variables

Testing the mediating variable of organizational citizenship behavior using the Bootstrapping (PROCESS) method proposed by Hayes (2013). Where the test results listed in Table 6 show that there is a mediating effect of organizational citizenship behavior about the relationship between intellectual capital and spiritual capital on organizational performance. From testing using the Bootstrapping method, it is known that the effect of the direct relationship of intellectual capital on organizational performance is 0.316 and is significant at the level of $p (0.003) < 0.05$. Meanwhile, to determine whether there is a mediating role of the OCB variable on the relationship between intellectual capital and organizational performance, it is by looking at the output indirect effect(s) of X on Y, where it is known that the mediation effect is significant with an indirect effect coefficient of 0.273, with a 95% confidence interval for BootLLCI (lower level for CI) is 0.052 and BootULCI (upper level for CI) is 0.498. If the BootLLCI and BootULCI ranges do not pass zero (0), it can be concluded that the estimation is significant and a mediating effect occurs (Hypothesis 3 is accepted).

Table 6: Hypothesis Testing the Role of OCB as Mediation

Total effect of X on Y							
	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c cs
Intellectual Capital	,5890	,0925	63,702	,0000	,4047	,7732	,5977
Spiritual Capital	,3872	,1338	28,936	,0050	,1205	,6539	,3208
Direct effect of X on Y							
	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c cs
Intellectual Capital	,3163	,1059	29,870	,0038	,1052	,5274	,3210
Spiritual Capital	-,0704	,1304	-,5402	,5907	-,3303	,1895	-,0583
Indirect effect(s) of X on Y							
		Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI			
X1 – OCB – Y	,2726	,1161	,0519	,4977			
X2 – OCB – Y	,4576	,1148	,2270	,6757			

Source: SPSS output (data processed)

Furthermore, in Table 6 it is also known that the direct effect of spiritual capital on organizational performance is -0.070 and not significant ($p = 0.591 > 0.05$). Meanwhile, to determine whether there is a mediating role of organizational citizenship behavior variables on the relationship of spiritual capital to organizational performance is to look at the output indirect effect(s) of X on Y, where it is known that the mediation effect is proven to be significant with an indirect effect coefficient of 0.458, with a 95% confidence interval in BootLLCI (lower level for CI) is 0.227 and BootULCI (upper level for CI) is 0.676. If the BootLLCI and BootULCI ranges do not pass zero (0), it can be concluded that the estimation is significant and a mediating effect occurs (Hypothesis 4 is accepted). The role of organizational citizenship behavior as a mediator in the relationship of the influence of spiritual capital on organizational performance has proven to be very crucial, where if the variable organizational citizenship behavior is not included in the model, then the direct relationship between spiritual capital and organizational performance is not significant.

DISCUSSION

Tourism has become a leading sector in the economy of many countries in the world, including Indonesia. The development of world modernization has brought very rapid changes in the tourism sector which have an impact on increasing the economy. The existence of tourist activities visiting tourist attractions in a country can encourage and increase the income of citizens and increase development in the area so that at a macro level it can increase the economic growth of a country. The development of the tourism sector which has an impact on the economy makes the country focus on increasing tourism by planning the application of strategies in an effort to win the competition for tourism visits from global tourists. Citing the opinion of Barney (1991) which asserts that if you want to win the competition, every organization/company must have competitive capital which is the company's resources.

In the company there are 2 forms of resources, namely intangible resources (intangible assets) and tangible resources (tangible assets). The meaning of intangible resources such as employees, organizational culture, company values, etc. Meanwhile, what is meant by tangible

resources within the company are machinery and operational support equipment. In the context of the state, efforts to promote tourism by relying on intangible resources as a source of competitive advantage is to prepare competent employees in every provincial and district/city tourism office in Indonesia. This is because the tourism office is the spearhead in the management of tourism in each region in Indonesia.

According to Clark et al, (2011) companies that have good performance resources are not solely located in object assets such as machines and buildings, but intellectual capital assets, not objects. An example of a non-profit organization is the Tourism Office, especially in Banda Aceh City. Organizational performance is not always seen how much it brings company profits, but how the community feels satisfied with good policies and services to the community, so that the presence of intellectual capital is considered important.

In this study, Hypothesis 1, namely testing the direct influence of intellectual capital on organizational performance, namely the Banda Aceh City Tourism Office, was proven positive and statistically significant ($p < 0.000 < 0.05$). This study proves and confirms the findings of previous researchers who describe the role of intellectual capital on organizational performance (Obeidat et al, 2017). For indirect testing with the variable organizational citizenship behavior as a mediator also proved significant (Hypothesis 3 accepted) is the relationship between the influence of intellectual capital on organizational performance. It is different with the results of Hypothesis 2 testing which proved not statistically significant, namely there is no direct relationship between spiritual capital on the organizational performance of the Banda Aceh City Tourism Office ($p > 0.824 > 0.05$). However, in indirect testing by including organizational citizenship behavior as a mediator variable into the relationship model of the influence of spiritual capital on organizational performance, it proved significant (Hypothesis 4).

The interesting thing was successfully revealed that the important role of organizational citizenship behavior as a mediator in the relationship of spiritual capital to organizational performance. The role of spiritual capital at the Banda Aceh City Tourism Office revealed that directly employees at the Tourism Office who already have a spiritual spirit at work who even work are considered worship and full of sincerity, have not been able to improve organizational performance without a sense of love and belonging to the organization (OCB). The researcher describes that this spiritual This culture is in line with the spirit of Islam that is applied in the Aceh region, where all government and private agencies should comply with and support sharia enforcement which is an attraction for local and foreign tourists..

Meanwhile, the spirit that comes from within is a sense of love and belonging to the organization. Organizational citizenship behavior possessed by employees is able to provide more motivation in building honesty for individuals at work, which in turn can improve organizational performance. A similar opinion was also expressed by Palmer and Wong (2013), that spiritual capital have significant effect on progress the organization, as spiritual intrinsic values can be controlled by the attitude of employees in certain situations, as well as the spiritual values of employees will encourage employees in order to better contribute to society and the organization. Employee spirituality has an influence on the way employees work, both in attitude and behavior (Baker & Smith, 2010).

The role of organizational citizenship behavior as a mediator is a determinant in maximizing the performance of an organization. It is expected that employees at the Banda Aceh City Tourist Institution must be able to behave in an organizational citizenship behavior, work together as a team, be willing to carry out additional work without complaints, help each other, save time in using company resources, give birth to ideas that build organizations (Peikani and Shamshiri, 2016). Finally, the organizational citizenship behavior possessed by the Banda Aceh City Tourism Office employees will make the organizational conditions mutually supportive to realize the vision, the mission and goals of the organization or with another intention is to want of make the Banda Aceh city as one of the leading domestic syariah tourist destinations.

V. CONCLUSION

Organizational performance at Banda Aceh City Tourism Institution is directly influenced by intellectual capital and the indirect role of organizational citizenship behavior as a mediator affects intellectual capital and spiritual capital on organizational performance. However, the role of organizational citizenship behavior has the most crucial role in the relationship between spiritual capital and organizational performance, where if there is no role for organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as a mediator, this direct relationship will not occur. With the superior intellectual capital owned by the Banda Aceh Tourism Office, is expected to be able to increase sharia tourism, and make Aceh one of the leading sharia tourism destinations in the archipelago.

The research results examined in this view are intellectual capital, spiritual capital and OCB play a major role in optimizing organizational performance achievements. Therefore, the Banda Aceh Tourism Office can recommend a number of policies, including: (1) centered on the development of organizational resources provide a variety of skills training, and appreciating every employee who excels, (2) create a strict Islamic (Syariah) culture in the organization as a basis for attitude and become the identity of employees, (3) build cooperative relationship with institutions/services/community organizations in order to build syariah tourism in Banda Aceh city. This problem needs to be implemented so that the community (stakeholders) feel they have ownership and are willing to collectively knit the sustainability of syariah tourism so that it continues to develop as a source of income for the region and the surrounding community in Banda Aceh City.

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